

season and 61.2 kg/ha in the second season. In both seasons, 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha were applied to rice as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash. The experiments were laid out in a split-plot design with four replications (see table).

Method of incorporation significantly influenced yield attributes and grain and

straw yields. Tractor-drawn cagewheel incorporation positively influenced rice productivity compared with the other methods (see table). This influence may be because of deeper incorporation (12.5 cm in the first season and 16.7 cm in the second season), which reduced considerably the loss of N and increased N availability to rice, resulting in higher yields.

Grain yield increased by 0.76 t/ha with tractor-drawn cagewheel incorporation and 0.30 t/ha with power tiller incorporation over animal-drawn implement incorporation. Tractor-drawn cagewheel incorporation with 100 kg added N/ha contributed to the highest yield in both seasons. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Mass culture of *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill. on rice hull

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Beauveria bassiana (Bals.) Vuill. shows potential as a biocontrol agent for many

Growth pattern (mean + SD conidial density × 10⁷/ml) of *Beauveria bassiana* on rice hull on different days of inoculation.

Amount of substrate	Days after inoculation			
	15	30	35	40
1/2 bag (180 g) (A)	1.50 ± 0.14	5.80 ± 0.60	5.00 ± 0.12	3.90 ± 0.27
3/4 bag (270 g) (B)	1.20 ± 0.19	5.00 ± 0.20	5.00 ± 0.11	4.90 ± 0.24

CV (%) = 7.71; CD_{0.01} (between A and B) = 0.1907 and (between days) = 0.2696.

insect pests of rice. To harvest large quantities of propagule to apply in the field, an easy, inexpensive process for mass culturing was developed. An autoclavable polypropylene bag (33 ×

17.5 cm) and a 3.5-cm-long × 3.2-cm-diameter piece of hollow dry bamboo are required.

The bamboo piece was fitted on the mouth of the bag with twine or a rubber band (see figure). Nonabsorbent cotton was used for plugging. Half to 3/4 of the bag was filled with rice hull (soaked in water overnight), 2% dextrose, and 0.05% chloramphenicol. Bags were sterilized at 20 lb pressure for 20 min, repeated for two consecutive days.

Inoculation was made with 1 ml of a 1.17×10^7 conidia/ml suspension and incubated at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 40 d. The bags were shaken thoroughly every 5 d for uniform growth of fungus. Conidial population was determined at 15, 30, 35, and 40 d after inoculation (DAI).

Twenty grams of substrate, obtained after thoroughly mixing the contents within each bag, was mixed in 70 ml of double-distilled water using Rottery mixture (Remi Motors, Remi Udyog, Bombay) for 20 min. The homogenate was filtered through muslin cloth and then through filter paper (Whatman no. 1). Conidia were counted from the filtrate using a haemocytometer (Naubauer, Fein-oplique, Beankenberg, GDR). The experiment was replicated five times and data were analyzed in a factorial complete randomized design.

Maximum fungal growth was obtained after 30-35 DAI (see table). Half-filled polypropylene bags yielded

Mass culturing *B. bassiana* on rice hull in an autoclavable polypropylene bag, a) hollow bamboo top, b) cotton plug, and c) polypropylene bag with hollow bamboo top and cotton plug fitted on the mouth.

the largest conidial population (5.8×10^7 conidia/ml) at 30 DAI, after which numbers gradually declined. Three-fourths-filled bags showed an unchanged conidial population from 30 to 35 DAI (5

$\times 10^7$ conidia/ml), after which it started declining.

Polypropylene pipes (autoclavable) may be used to replace the hollow dry bamboo pieces. This technique is supe-

Integrated pest management—insects

Metarrhizium sp.: a new biocontrol agent for brown planthopper management in ricefields

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Agronomic practices and use of certain insecticides are the reported causes of increases in brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) populations. Continued use of insecticides was reported to be responsible for BPH epidemics in Sri Lanka, India, Philippines, and Indonesia.

We found that the fungus *Metarrhizium* sp. isolated from infected BPH in an untreated Sri Lankan ricefield caused very high mortality in BPH populations. Pathogenicity of the isolate AB301/1 was studied using BPH collected from wetland ricefields. Healthy BPH were reared on 2-mo-old rice plants of cultivar BG90-2 raised in clay pots (10 cm diam, 15 cm high), with 2.5 cm standing water. Plants were raised in a greenhouse at $30 \pm 4^\circ\text{C}$ and 60-75% RH. Twenty-five 18-d-old BPH in these pots were later sprayed with an atomizer containing 6.4×10^6 spores/ml of *Metarrhizium* sp. Treatments were replicated 10 times with distilled water

spray as a control. Pots were observed for dead insects every 24 h for 8 d.

The pathogen sporulated on the surface of BPH. Infected hoppers appeared green and died within a few days. With the spore concentration used, we observed a significantly high mortality of 64.8% ($t = 16.97$ at $p = 0.05$ and $df = 18$).

In a similar experiment, concentrations of 0 , 6.4×10^3 , 6.4×10^4 , 6.4×10^5 , 6.4×10^6 , and 6.4×10^7 fungal spores/ml were sprayed onto 18-d-old BPH on 30-d-old-rice plants raised in pots (20 plants/pot) with standing water. Percentage mortality recorded was adjusted for mortality in control treatments using Abbott's formula (see table). The highest mortality rate (76%) was observed on the seventh day after spraying when a spore concentration of 6.4×10^5 was used. Further increase or decrease in spore concentrations produced a lower mortality rate. It is possible that while lower rates of spore concentration do not provide enough coverage, higher concentrations show self-limiting antagonistic effects on infection. We propose that *Metarrhizium* sp. be used as an effective agent in integrated pest management programs in combating BPH problems in wetland rice culture.

Percentage mortality of *Nilaparvata lugens* treated with various concentrations of *Metarrhizium* sp. (AB301/1).^a

<i>Metarrhizium</i> spores/ml concentration	Days after treatment with spores						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6.4×10^7	0	0	0	3.3	6.6	20.0	33.3
6.4×10^6	0	0	16.6	26.6	30.0	50.0	56.6
6.4×10^5	0	6.6	10.0	26.6	33.3	53.3	76.6
6.4×10^4	0	6.6	10.0	10.0	13.3	16.6	20.0
6.4×10^3	0	3.3	3.3	3.3	6.6	6.6	10.0

^aMortality values are adjusted for control treatment values using Abbott's formula.

rior to inoculating fungus through a slit made on the body of the bag because it reduces contamination. ■

Flight activity of *Spodoptera fugiperda* (J. E. Smith) in acid savanna ricefields in northeastern Colombia

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Precise information on pest population dynamics is needed for implementing integrated pest management (IPM) programs. Since rice was introduced to the acid savanna soils in northeastern Colombia, farmers have complained that the fall armyworm (FAW) *Spodoptera fugiperda* (J. E. Smith) causes economic damage and reduced yields. Farmers often use up to two insecticide applications per season to control the pest without knowing the pest population dynamics and density.

A 3-yr study was conducted to determine flying patterns of *S. fugiperda* adults in commercial savanna rice-growing areas of Colombia. At each of three localities in the Cauca Department, two sticky traps with pheromone lures were placed within ricefields, 1 m above the ground. Lures were replaced every 45 d. Adults/trap were recorded twice a month. The mean number of adults/month was calculated for each locality (see table).

In general, the mean number of adults/month was low across three localities. The most collected was 34 males/trap during January at Santa Rosa and La Libertad, although rice is planted from April to early June. Eleven males/trap were counted at Matazul during July, but FAW population was below 5 males/trap during most of the year. This high number at Matazul coincides with the commercial rice-growing season, while the higher infestation rates at Santa Rosa and La Libertad occur when no rice was in the fields. This suggests that FAW population increases at Santa Rosa and La